

CYCLE GRAPH SCHEDULE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 STUDENTS IN CARVER MIDDLE SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to find the impact of cycle graph schedule to the academic performance of Grade 6 students in Carver Middle School. The study utilized a quasi-experimental design using a one-group pretest and posttest in which the outcome of interest is measured 2 times: once before and once after exposing the respondents to a certain intervention. The respondents were exposed to pretest for six days and they were given an intervention after the assessment. They were then given a posttest to measure their understanding after completing the discussions. The data were then collected, tallied and tabulated. Based on the data analysis, it was found out that the impact of cycle graph schedule in the academic performance of the Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed both Pretest and Post Test is in Average Progress. The paper concluded that gender and mathematics level of the respondents are not determining factors that affect the impact of cycle graph schedule to their academic performance because it was found out that there is no significant difference between them after several tests were conducted.

Keywords: *Cycle Graph Schedule, Academic Performance, Intervention, Assessment, Average progress*

INTRODUCTION

The situation today is the most challenging phase in the educational system all over the world due to the different global problems people experience today. All educational institutions were affected by the Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) where it prohibited the traditional face-to-face learning modality. This disease played a big impact in education because the learning never stopped. Modular Distance Learning Modality (MDL), Online Distance Learning Modality (ODL) and Hybrid Learning were suggested by the different experts to flatten the curves in learning.

Mathematics is one of the most important subjects in our human life. Without the knowledge in mathematics, we can say nothing is possible in the world (Acharya, 2017). The latest results of an international exam given to teenagers ranked the USA ninth in reading and 31st in math literacy out of 79 countries and economies. America has a smaller-than-average share of top-performing math students, and scores have essentially been flat for two decades. The average scores, from tests given last fall, declined 4 points in reading and 9 points in math, compared with tests given in the 2019-2020 school year, and are the lowest in decades. The math scores were even more disappointing. On a scale of 500 points, the declines ranged from 6 to 8 points for middle and high performing students, to 12 to 14 points for low performing students.

In the recent study on the math scores of each individual state from the 2021 SAT Suite Results from the College Board, the state of Florida has the lowest math score in the U.S. at 50 points below the benchmark, with an average score of 480 (Brown,2023). In addition, among the 50 States of America, Florida ranked 32nd on the National Assessment of Educational Progress, which the U.S. Department of Education bills as The Nation's Report Card.

The average score for students in Florida in 2022 (271) was lower than their average score in 2019 (279) and was not significantly different from their average score in 2003 (271). Looking at these views, these serious problems in Mathematics level of the students must be addressed systematically. This needs urgency in addressing the gaps to attain quality education in the United States.

There are many things to consider about the decline of students' mathematics achievement level. Some students are catching up, but time is running out for others. Every student experienced the pandemic differently, and there is tremendous variation from student to student, with certain populations—namely, Black, Hispanic, and low-income students, as well as other vulnerable populations—suffering the most severe impacts (Lake and Pillow,2022).

Violence in schools is a rising issue and bullying is a key contributor. According to the National Center for Education Statistics, over 20% of students in grades 6 through 12 have been bullied either in school or on their way to/from school. This figure is actually down from 32% in 2007 but is still much too high. The challenge with these statistics is that many students who are bullied do NOT report it. Bullied students experience a wide

range of physical, behavioral, and emotional problems that can impact not only their education but also their lives (Barrington, 2023).

Teachers in public schools can only do so much to support their students. When the students go home for the day, the state of their home life can impact their development both personally and academically. In cases where parents lack higher education, they may not be able to provide the assistance students need to learn and to complete homework. Students in low-income families face additional challenges at home, though even middle- and upper-class families aren't off the hook. In many families, parents are too career-focused and have little time to spend supporting their child's education (Barrington, 2023).

These are some of the biggest failures of the American Public Education System. To solve these issues, each county in different states has their own method of scheduling classes. Some of which are the traditional period scheduling, block schedule and rotation schedule.

The School District of Palm Beach County is one of the school districts in Florida which uses the rotation scheduling which is also a cycle graph schedule where the teacher meets their students in different time frames. Thus, this research study has the main objective of finding the impact of cycle graph schedule in the academic performance of Grade 6 students in Carver Middle School.

Review of Related Literature

This chapter presents the Chronological Relationship of the Reviewed Literature & Studies with the present investigation/study.

In the study conducted by Keller in 1997 about The Effect of three different types of high school class schedules (traditional, rotating block, and accelerated block) on high school biology achievement and on differences in science learning environments, she found out that student achievement was significantly different for each of the scheduled comparison groups, test score means were not statistically significant between the schedule comparison groups for different ethnic groups, economically disadvantaged students, and magnet students.

In the study conducted by Heger in 2006 entitled "A Comparison of Achievement Level in Mathematics and Science and Current Attitudes of Secondary Students in a Six-Period Daily Schedule, With Those of Students in a Rotate-Eight Block Schedule", he found out that no statistically significant results or trends based on treatment were discovered as main effects or interactions in part one. The achievement gap between African-American and Caucasian students was confirmed in all achievement measures except science GPA, where only ability, not ethnicity or treatment, was found to be of significance as a main effect. Though not of statistical significance, a pattern favoring low ability REB subgroups and high ability SPD subgroups was noted. Analysis of survey results indicated that groups and subgroups differed significantly in scores for effectiveness of the schedules overall, and for the classroom activities subscale.

The study of Schott in 2008 about “From block to traditional schedule: The impact on academic achievement, attendance rates, and dropout rates”, he mentioned that statistical analysis revealed varied results in mean scores for math academic achievement and attendance rates, but no statistically significant difference.

There are several factors that affect the achievement level of students in Mathematics. In the study conducted by Liu in 2009 about An Investigation of Factors Affecting Gender Differences in Standardized Math Performance: Results from U.S. and Hong Kong 15 Year Olds, she said that learning strategies and affective factors could have a profound impact on student standardized mathematics performance. In addition, she found out that U.S. students' interest in math was significantly negatively related to their math performance. Contrary to a widely reported finding that East Asian students emphasize memorization, U.S. students were found to heavily rely on memorization strategies, which was also a negative predictor of math achievement.

In a 2013 study by Hockney about The Impact of High School Schedule Type on Instructional Effectiveness and Student Achievement in Mathematics, there were no significant differences found in the percent of students meeting or exceeding standards on the 2011 PSAT between schools on a block schedule versus those on a traditional schedule. The analysis showed that teachers currently on a traditional schedule rated the traditional schedule higher than those currently teaching on a block schedule. Teachers currently teaching on a block schedule rated the block schedule more favorably than teachers currently teaching on a traditional schedule. However, teachers currently teaching on a block schedule rated the traditional schedule as the most effective overall for most of the student outcomes.

Among the factors identified as militating against students' performance in the department of mathematics are: inadequacy of mathematics lecturers, teaching methods, students' attitudes and interests, lecturers' qualifications, inadequacy of textbooks, especially indigenous authors, inadequacy of evaluation, and rated high was inadequacy of human resources, followed by lecturers-students interaction, lack of textbooks, and lecturers' qualifications (Ali, 2013).

In the study conducted by Emmons in 2017 entitled “Timed Test and Math Anxiety as Factors Affecting Elementary School Math Performance, he mentioned that no differences were found between the math anxiety scores of males and females.

Study habits, time management, and attitude towards mathematics are the factors that affect underachievement in mathematics (Suan, 2018).

A rotating standard bell schedule is similar to a standard bell schedule in that students attend each of their classes each day and each class is generally the same length each day, but instead of each class period meeting at a fixed time each day, each class meets during a different period each day (Bacon, 2021). He further explained that the advantage of a rotating standard schedule is that students often enjoy the variation in their schedule each day breaking up the monotony of a standard bell schedule, and it has

the potential to reduce behavioral issues such as after lunch. Additionally, for students that have to be frequently absent for extracurricular activities, a cycle graph schedule reduces the impact on any one class due to these absences.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the Impact of Rotation Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Gender;
 - 1.2. Mathematics Level?
2. What is the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the pre and post test?
3. Is there a significant difference on the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of:
 - 3.1. Gender;
 - 3.2. Mathematics Level?
4. Is there a significant difference on the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the pre and posttest?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

This research study was conducted at Carver Middle School during the fiscal year 2023-2024. Carver Middle School is one of the Title I school in the School District of Palm Beach located at 101 Barwick Road, Delray Beach, Florida, United States of America. The said school is under the Title I program which are designed to improve academic outcomes for all students

Sampling Method

The respondents of this study are the 20 students from Period 5 class of the researcher who were selected by a cluster sampling. Cluster random sampling is a probability sampling method where researchers divide a large population into smaller groups known as clusters, and then select randomly among the clusters to form a sample (Simkus, 2023). The classes were divided into five clusters and Period 5 class was selected. All of the students in this class were included in the sample and this period ideally mirrors the characteristics of the population as a whole.

Data Gathering Procedure

This research deals with finding The Impact of Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School. The researcher created Pre and Post Tests and submitted them to three Mathematics Teachers for validation of the instrument. When these instruments were already validated, he administered the Pretest to his Period 5 class for 6 days. After collecting the data from this assessment, an intervention was made before the researcher administered the Posttest. The researcher collected the data. He separated the results between the Pretest and the Posttest. Using different statistical treatments, data were computed, analyzed and interpreted.

Instrument

This study used the researcher's made Pretest and Post Test. Both tests are only 10 items which cover the Benchmarks for Excellent Student Thinking (B.E.S.T.) in Mathematics 6. The tests were aligned in Units 3 and 4 of Florida Standards Quizzes (FSQs) for Mathematics 6. Both tests were carefully created by the researcher and Mathematics Teachers validated the items in the tests. After that, the researcher administered the tests to the respondents of this research.

Rating Description for Pretest and Post Test

Score Range	Rating Description	Interpretation
9.00-10.00	Outstanding Progress	Mastery level performance; learning goals exceeded
8.00-8.99	Above Average Progress	Strong understanding; on track with expectations.
7.00-7.99	Average Progress	Meets minimum expectations; satisfactory performance.
6.00-6.99	Lowest Acceptable Progress	Below average; needs targeted support to improve.
0.00-5.99	Failure	Well below expectations; immediate intervention recommended.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The following statistical tools were utilized for the appropriate treatment of the data gathered. Frequency and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of Gender and Mathematics Level. To determine the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the pre and post test, average was used. T-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference on the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of Gender, and in terms of Mathematics Level, One Way ANOVA was used. To determine if there is a significant difference on the impact of the rotation schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the pre and posttest, t-test was used.

Scope and Limitations

This study focuses on the impact of recycle graph schedule to the academic performance of the Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School. The data collected was conducted to the 20 students of Period 5 class of the researcher.

This Period 5 class meets their teacher in 6 different time frames. The teacher utilized the use of Pre and Post Tests which were given to the students in 6 different time schedules. The profile of the respondents used in order to find the significant difference between the results are their gender and mathematics level as revealed by their PM 1 scores in Florida Assessment of Student Thinking Scores.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion discusses the findings obtained from the researcher's Pre and Post Test Furthermore, it interprets and analyzes data gathered based on the instrument given to the respondents.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents' Profile
in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	11	55%
Female	9	45%
Total	20	100%

Table 1 shows the Frequency and Percentage of the respondent's profile in terms of gender. It could be seen on the table that 11 or 55% of the respondents are males and 9 or 45% of the respondents are females. This means that males outnumbered females

in terms of this profile. This implies that there is a 10% gap on the data gathered between the respondents' gender.

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents' Profile
in Terms of Mathematics Level

Mathematics Level	Frequency	Percentage
Level 1	11	55%
Level 2	6	30%
Level 3	2	10%
Level 4	1	5%
Total	20	100%

Table 2 shows the Frequency and Percentage of the respondent's profile in terms of mathematics level. It could be gleaned on the table that 11 or 55% of the respondents are in Level 1, 6 or 30% are in Level 2, 2 or 10% are in Level 3 and 1 or 5% of the respondents is in Level 4. This means that Level 1 ranked first, Level 2 ranked second and Levels 3 and 4 ranked 3rd and fourth respectively. This implies that there is a huge gap in the data gathered between the respondents' mathematics level.

Table 3
The Impact of Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6
Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by Pretest

Time Frame Schedule	Average	Interpretation	Rank
9:30 am - 10:20 am	6.21	Lowest Acceptable Progress	6
10:25 am - 11:15 am	8.21	Above Average Progress	1
11:20 am - 1:25 pm	7.75	Average Progress	2
1:30 pm - 2:20 pm	7.37	Average Progress	3
2:25 pm- 3:15 pm	7.22	Average Progress	4
3:20 pm -4:10 pm	6.80	Lowest Acceptable Progress	5
Overall Average	7.26	Average Progress	

It could be seen on the table that the 10:25 am- 11:15 am schedule has the highest average which is 8.21 and is verbally interpreted as above average progress. The

schedules from 11:20 am-1:25 am, 1:30 pm-2:20 pm and 2:25 pm - 3:15 pm have an average of 7.75, 7.37 and 7.22 respectively and are verbally interpreted as average progress. Furthermore, the schedules from 9:30 am - 10:20 am and 3:20 pm -4:10 pm have an average of 6.21 and 6.80 and both are verbally interpreted as lowest acceptable progress. This could mean that students performed better when the assessment is given to them in the second period before they take their lunch and students performed poorly when the assessment is given to them in the first period as revealed by the pretest.

The overall impact of the cycle graph schedule in the academic performance of the Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the Pretest has an average of 7.26 and is verbally interpreted as an Average Progress. This would mean that the respondents still achieved a passing rate set by the School District of Palm Beach in Pretest considering the diverse time frame schedule.

Table 4

The Impact of Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by Posttest

Time Frame Schedule	Average	Interpretation	Rank
9:30 am - 10:20 am	6.15	Lowest Acceptable Progress	6
10:25 am - 11:15 am	9.05	Outstanding Progress	1
11:20 am - 1:25 pm	8.45	Above Average Progress	2
1:30 pm - 2:20 pm	7.65	Average Progress	3
2:25 pm- 3:15 pm	7.00	Average Progress	5
3:20 pm -4:10 pm	7.40	Average Progress	4
Overall Average	7.62	Average Progress	

Table 4 shows the Impact of Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by Posttest.

It could be deduced from the table that the 10:25 am- 11:15 am schedule has the highest average which is 9.05 and is verbally interpreted as outstanding progress. The schedule from 11:20 am-1:25 am has an average of 8.45 and is verbally interpreted as above average progress. The schedules from 1:30 pm-2:20 pm, 2:25 pm - 3:15 pm and 3:20 pm - 4:10 pm have an average of 7.65, 7.00 and 7.40 respectively and are verbally interpreted as average progress. Furthermore, the schedule from 9:30 am - 10:20 am has an average of 6.15 and is verbally interpreted as lowest acceptable progress. This could mean that students performed better when the assessment is given to them in the second period before they take their lunch and students performed poorly when the assessment is given to them in the first period as revealed by the posttest. The results have a

consistent performance in the Pretest where the students performed better in the 10:25 am - 11:15 am schedule and performed poorly in the 9:30 am - 10:20 am schedule.

The overall impact of the cycle graph schedule in the academic performance of the Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School as revealed by the Posttest has an average of 7.62 and is verbally interpreted as an Average Progress. This would mean that the respondents still achieved a passing rate set by the School District of Palm Beach in Posttest considering the diverse time frame schedule.

Table 5

Significant Difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in Terms of Gender as revealed by Pretest

Gender	n	Mean	t-cal	t-crit	df	p	D	I
Male	11	6.83	0.97	2.11	18	0.34	A	NS
Female	9	7.79						

Table 5 shows the significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of gender as revealed by Pretest.

It can be seen on the table that the calculated t- value is 0.97 which is less than the critical t-ratio of 2.11. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of gender as revealed by Pretest is accepted.

It is supported by the study conducted by Emmons in 2017 entitled "Timed Test and Math Anxiety as Factors Affecting Elementary School Math Performance where he mentioned that no differences were found between the math anxiety scores of males and females.

Table 6 on the next page shows the significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of mathematics level as revealed by Pretest.

Table 6
Significant Difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in Terms of Mathematics Level as revealed by Pretest

Sources	SS	df	MS	F	F crit	p	D	I
Between	28.17	5	5.63	0.86	2.30	0.51	A	NS
Within	696.08	106	6.57					

It can be gleaned on the table that the calculated f- value is 0.86 which is less than the critical f-ratio of 2.30. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of mathematics level as revealed by Pretest is accepted. This means that the achievement level of the students in Mathematics is not a significant factor that affects the impact of rotation schedule to their performance.

Table 7
Significant Difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in Terms of Gender as revealed by Posttest

Gender	n	Mean	t-cal	t-crit	df	P	D	I
Male	11	7.42	0.18	2.14	18	0.86	A	NS
Female	9	7.63						

Table 7 shows the significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of gender as revealed by Posttest.

It can be seen on the table that the calculated t- value is 0.18 which is less than the critical t-ratio of 2.14. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of gender as revealed by Posttest is accepted. This means that gender is not a determining factor that affects the impact of rotation schedule to their performance.

Table 8

Significant Difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in Terms of Mathematics Level as revealed by Posttest

Sources	SS	df	MS	F	F crit	p	D	I
Between	78.17	5	15.63	1.85	2.29	0.11	A	NS
Within	965.8	114	8.47					

Table 8 shows the significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of mathematics level as revealed by Posttest.

It can be gleaned on the table that the calculated f- value is 1.85 which is less than the critical f-ratio of 2.29. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of mathematics level as revealed by Posttest is accepted. This means that the achievement level of the students in Mathematics is not a significant factor that affects the impact of rotation schedule to their performance.

Table 9

Significant Difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in Terms of Pretest and Posttest

Tests	n	Mean	t-cal	t-crit	df	p	D	I
Pretest	6	7.26	-0.81	2.57	5	0.45	A	NS
Posttest	6	7.62						

Table 9 shows the significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of Pretest and Posttest.

It can be seen on the table that the calculated t- value is -0.81 which is less than the critical t-ratio of 2.57. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the Impact of the Cycle Graph Schedule to the Academic Performance of Grade 6 Students in Carver Middle School in terms of Pretest and Posttest is accepted.

This means that no difference was found between the two assessments taken by the respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the results, it can be concluded that Gender is not a determining factor that affects the impact of the cycle graph schedule on the academic performance of the Grade 6 students in Carver Middle School. In addition, Mathematics Level is not a determining factor that affects the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the academic performance of the Grade 6 students in Carver Middle School. Furthermore, Pretest and Posttest results have the same interpretation on the impact of the cycle graph schedule to the academic performance of the Grade 6 students in Carver Middle School. Students performed better if the assessment was given to them before lunch period. Students performed poorly if the assessment was given to them in the first-time frame schedule of the day.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher hereby proposed to use other variables aside from gender and mathematics level in determining the significant difference on the impact of cycle graph schedule to the academic performance of the respondents. The remaining standards in Florida Assessment of Student Thinking (FAST) may be crafted following the created Pretest and Posttest. Future researchers may conduct parallel studies with a large number of respondents. The researcher also recommends for future researchers to conduct parallel studies with controlled and experimental groups.

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